

The Delusion of a Long-Term Diplomatic Resolution Without Political Transformation

Jonathan Graubart

Jonathan Graubart is a Professor of Political Science at San Diego State, USA. His most recent publication is “Jewish Self-Determination Beyond Zionism: Lessons from Hannah Arendt and Other Pariahs,” Temple University Press, 2023. Email: graubart@sdsu.edu

There is no shortage of misconceptions about Israel’s Gaza offensive. The most egregious one is locating the conflict’s onset on October 7 when Hamas and its allies killed nearly 1200 people and abducted over 250 back to Gaza. Pro-Israel advocates invoke this narrative to deem Hamas culpable for all the ensuing devastation inflicted on Gazans. A less frequently circulated misconception, of appeal in some Palestine-solidarity circles, is that the Gaza horrors and all past ones stem entirely from the creation of a Jewish settler-colonial state forged through ethnic cleansing.

The misconception I wish to highlight is that most common in U.S. and allied diplomatic circles. This holds that there is a diplomatic path for enticing Israeli and Palestinian political leaders to reach a peaceful resolution. This misconception flies in the face of entrenched internal political dysfunctions in both communities.

Contrary to official U.S. claims, but well documented in human rights reports, Israel is not a liberal democracy but a regime that maintains Jewish domination across all greater Israel, which includes the West Bank, East Jerusalem, and Gaza, and perpetrates egregious human rights abuses of Palestinians

in the West Bank and Gaza. Its current governing coalition consists of hardline nationalist parties, including one inspired by the late Meir Kahane, an outspoken racist and advocate of ethnic cleansing. Even if Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu is voted out of office, the hard-right and intolerant attitudes of Israeli Jews ensure that the illiberal, racist, and violent policies will endure. The full viciousness of this political culture is on display in the relentless Gaza offensive coupled with the widespread racist and often genocidal statements from politicians, soldiers, journalists, and regular citizens.

The formal Palestinian political institutions consist primarily of the PLO-led Palestinian Authority (PA) in the West Bank and Hamas in the Gaza Strip. Because Israel asserts ultimate control over both territories and aims to keep Palestinians weak and fragmented, both political entities are severely limited in governing capacity. Yet even factoring in these restrictions, Palestinian politics has moved in a distressing direction since the formation of the PA in the early 1990s. Palestinians are caught between an authoritarian Fatah-led PA with no popular legitimacy and an oppressive Hamas, whose normalization of violence, as Tareq Baconi (2018, 243) concludes, has “threatened to erode the very social fabric of the Palestinian community under occupa-

tion.”

In short, neither Israelis nor Palestinians have political institutions equipped to take the bold steps needed to reach a just and lasting resolution. The U.S. and allies conveniently remain in denial of this reality, hoping that a path can be found if only Hamas and the most extremist coalition parties in Israel can somehow be marginalized. Indeed, the U.S. keeps propping up Israel and, to a much lesser extent, the PA, with military or internal security assistance.

To be sure, the recent decision of the Biden Administration not to block a UN Security Council resolution demanding a ceasefire gives hope that there will soon be a halt to Israeli's onslaught. But a broader diplomatic resolution is not possible under existing political realities. The only way to end the cycle of death and misery, whose impact falls overwhelmingly on Palestinians, is to transform the political institutions in both societies. In “Truth and Reconciliation,” the late Edward Said (2001, 319) appealed to a vanguard of Palestinian and Jewish iconoclasts who possess an “innovative, daring, and theoretical willingness to get beyond the arid stalemate of assertion, exclusivism, and rejection.”

Such iconoclasts are present in Palestine-Israel and the diaspora. Guided by Said's insight, political scientists should diagnose the political dysfunctions of all protagonists, identify the vanguard constituencies, and find lessons for how these actors can reach a critical mass. ♦

References

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